

National Dysphoria: a terminology and a research proposal

Domina Petric, MD

ABSTRACT

National dysphoria may be defined as a state of unease or dissatisfaction with one's own nationality and national identity. It may be caused by national trauma, such as during and after aggression by another nation, extreme globalization, in which the sovereignty of individual nations and individual states is being wiped out, or in the case of being a victim of totalitarianism (classical, soft, inverted).

INTRODUCTION

National identity may be defined as a person's identity or sense of belonging to one state or to one nation^{1,2}. It is a sense of a nation as cohesive whole, as represented by distinctive traditions, culture, and language³. National identity may refer to the subjective feeling individual shares with a group of people about a nation, regardless of one's legal citizenship status⁴. National identity is viewed in psychological terms as an awareness of difference, a feeling and recognition of what is *we* and *they*⁵. National identity can arise as a direct result of the presence of elements from the common points in people's daily lives: national symbols, language, the nation's history, national consciousness, and cultural artefacts⁶.

Patriotism can be defined as the expression of one's national identity seen in a positive light and characterized by national pride and love for one's country, whilst chauvinism is the extreme expression of national identity, which refers to the firm belief in the country's superiority and extreme loyalty toward one's country¹.

NATIONAL DYSPHORIA

National dysphoria may be defined as a state of unease or dissatisfaction with one's own nationality and national identity. It may be caused by national trauma, such as during and after aggression by another nation, extreme globalization, in which the sovereignty of individual nations and individual states is being wiped out, or in the case of extreme abuse and unjust persecution conducted by a totalitarian government.

Chauvinism is characteristic for conquerors, imperialists, colonialists..., that is nations who believe in their superiority in comparison to the nations they attack. Nations that are under attack, conquered nations, can develop national inferiority complex that becomes a part of a national consciousness. As a consequence of wars many individuals who belong to defeated nations may lose their healthy sense of national identity and even opt for another nationality, culture and religion. National trauma is a concept in social psychology, that can be defined as a trauma in which the effects of a trauma apply generally to the members of a collective

group⁷. National trauma may be a risk factor for the development of national dysphoria.

As the world becomes increasingly globalized, international tourism, communication and business collaboration has increased⁸. Globalization promotes common values and experiences, and it also encourages the identification with the global community⁹. People may adapt cosmopolitanism and view themselves as global beings, or world citizens¹⁰. This trend may threaten national identity because globalization undermines the importance of being a citizen of a particular country¹¹. Several researchers found that as a country becomes more globalized, patriotism declined, which suggests that the increase of globalization is associated with less loyalty and less willingness to fight for one's own country^{8, 12, 13}.

An individual can have the national identity and be the citizen of the world at the same time, but extreme globalization might jeopardize the healthy sense of national identity. The idea of the one world government might not be promising, because it might represent a risk factor for the development of global totalitarian regime. Division of world power on national governments who cooperate with each other in promoting public good might better protect world democracy than the one world government in which the power would be too centralized and in the hands of extremely rich and powerful individuals. Extreme globalization might also be a risk factor for the development of national dysphoria.

In corrupted states, individuals who oppose to the corrupted regime might be subjected to extreme persecution, systemic abuse and torture, which can altogether cause national dysphoria. Soft totalitarianism

is a type of totalitarianism based on the cancel culture¹⁴, which may be defined as a desire to cancel out a person or community from social media platforms, professional and social life. In soft totalitarianism political and economic elite use their power, influence and money to cancel whoever they want from public, social and professional life. Victim of a soft totalitarianism can become socially isolated, blocked from having a career and even a private life. Such state of extreme social isolation in one's own country and nation may lead to the development of national dysphoria.

The political philosopher Sheldon Wolin coined the term inverted totalitarianism in 2003 to describe what he saw as the emerging form of government of the United States¹⁵. Characteristics of inverted totalitarianism are exploitation of the legal and political constraints of the established democratic system in order to use these constraints to defeat their original purpose; managed democracy which applies managerial skills to basic democratic political institutions; illusion of a free press because information is governed by highly concentrated media corporations (censorship); strong democracy defined as *our democracy* instead of everyone's democracy; profit of multinational corporations and powerful individuals (billionaires) is a priority (above the public good); corporations through lobbying, political contributions and the revolving door dominate, with the government acting as the servant of large corporations (this is considered normal rather than corrupt); extreme globalization; encouragement of political apathy of the people, whilst ruling elite has clear political goals; economy of fear as a method

of punishment for disobedient individuals (minimization of social security, financial crisis that only affects middle and working class); political leaders are akin to corporate leaders; exploitation of the poor by reducing health and social programs and weakening working conditions. Inverted totalitarianism might also be a risk factor for the development of national dysphoria.

CONCLUSION

National dysphoria may be defined as a state of unease or dissatisfaction with one's own nationality and national identity. Risk factors for the development of national dysphoria might be national trauma, extreme globalization, corruption, cancel culture, and totalitarianism (classical, soft, inverted). More research is mandatory in order to better define here-proposed new term as well as its social and psychological implications.

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